

Artificial Intelligence: Boon or Bane?

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Abstract: Humans are the images of God and are created with plethora of potentials. They are endowed with the capacities and capabilities to create anything for the wellbeing of all creatures. Latest technologies prove that. If a human is an image of God, then, all things come through his/her knowledge are also images of God. Of all inventions and discoveries, Artificial Intelligence has become the crown of all. It enhances the lives of all creatures living in the world. All things have positive sides. It is the person who uses it determines whether it is helpful or harmful. Whatever we do or invent should assist to build up the Kingdom of God on this soil and lead the human race toward peace and joy. AI also comes under this criterion. We the image of God have the divine and moral obligation to use AI responsibly. AI which was invented for the good of humans becomes harmful and brings negative impacts on all of us. In this essay, what are the benefits of AI, what are the challenges that the world is facing now, and what is the standpoint of the Church on AI are discussed in this essay.

Introduction

These are times of great technological leaps. A technological revolution could be defined as a powerful group of technologies, products and new industries, capable of shaking the economy and boosting an era of development. In the twenty-first century, we are in front of a gigantic number of technological innovations. In this context, artificial intelligence

(AI) is highlighted as the most important, because it places us in the frontier between man and machine.

Is AI a threat or an opportunity to the worker? Does its introduction to the system of production and services provoke a reduction in the number of jobs to the point that could bring about an end to human labour? Or, on the contrary, will AI drive the rise of employment and income? What are its negative consequences for human labour? Unemployment, precariousness and social exclusion? What could be the opportunities to the world of labour offered by AI? Could we risk making some predictions about the future of labour?¹

1. What is AI?

Artificial intelligence is the study of mental faculties through the use of computational models.² Artificial Intelligence is generally understood as the possession of intelligence or the exercise of thinking by computers or machines.³ The working definition of AI can be formulated as enabling machines to know, understand, judge things, and feel things as they are programmed.

Basically, AI can be viewed from two angles or dimensions:

1. Human performance
2. Rationality

Each of these dimensions has four approaches

1. Thinking Humanly
2. Thinking Rationally
3. Acting Humanly
4. Acting Rationally⁴

AI is actually looking to simulate human brain functions rather than mere intelligence; human consciousness deserves our serious attention. Rather than intelligence, consciousness is more unique to human beings. Taking into account this, Roger Penrose presented

¹ Elio Gasda, "Artificial Intelligence: The Future of Labour and Employment," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 645 - 646.

² Charniak, Eugene, and Drew McDermott, *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence* (New Delhi: Dorling Kindersley (India) Pvt. Ltd, 2009), 6.

³ John Kennedy Philip, "A Cosmo-ethical Assessment of Artificial Intelligence," *Jnanodaya Journal of Philosophy* 25, no.1 (June 2018), 178.

⁴ Angelo Chakkanattu, "Human Natural Machine Intelligence of Evolution," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 569.

four different viewpoints which he gathered from the arguments of various researchers.⁵

A. Thinking as well as a human feeling of conscious awareness is computational.

B. Any physical action can be simulated computationally, but computational simulation cannot by itself evoke awareness.

C. Any physical action which evokes awareness cannot be simulated computationally.

D. Awareness cannot be explained by physical, computational, or any other scientific terms.⁶

2. Benefits of AI

2.1. Using Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare

1. First, artificial intelligence is used to diagnose degenerative diseases

2. Second, in operating rooms, AI helps to guide robots and augments the precision of surgeons in their complex surgeries,

3. Finally, in drug research, by examining more than 100 million molecules, AI identifies new types of antibiotics effective against a wide range of bacteria now considered untreatable, including resistant strains of tuberculosis. A new

⁵ Gregory Mathew Malayil, "Will Artificial Intelligence Replace the Human Being? A Critical Analysis of the Views of Roger Penrose and Stephen Hawking with Theological Reflections," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 605.

⁶ Gregory Mathew Malayil, 606.

antibiotic, called halicin,⁷ is the first discovered with artificial intelligence.⁸

2.2. AI Promises Exponential Economic Growth

Prior to the Industrial Revolution, when human beings were mainly involved in the agricultural sector, the rate of economic growth was less and slow. After the Industrial Revolution when machines were utilized in production, the rate of economic growth was more and more rapid. Since 2013 with an application of AI technology in the economy, the world is hopefully seeing exponential economic growth. Therefore, the world is choosing to move rapidly toward the digital economy.⁹ AI generates economic growth, increases profit margins, reduces prices, and increases demand, at the same time it creates new jobs that make up for the ones that disappear.¹⁰

2.3. Opportunities through AI

AI also offers opportunities. Self-driving vehicles, algorithm negotiation in the stock market, and medical diagnosis are examples of processes where AI has the potential to raise quality, efficiency, and productivity and income levels. Robots are offering the skills that companies seek in people.¹¹

AI is an advanced form of computing that, conjugated with 650 robotics, can exponentially increase productivity and quality in many sectors of the economy, since it optimizes the execution of tasks trusted to human beings. The machines not only could do

⁷ The researchers say the antibiotic, called halicin, is the first discovered with artificial intelligence (AI). Although AI has been used to aid parts of the antibiotic-discovery process before, they say that this is the first time it has identified completely new kinds of antibiotic from scratch, without using any previous human assumptions. The work, led by synthetic biologist Jim Collins at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in Cambridge, is published in *Cell*. (<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-00018-3>) accessed on 30.01.2023.

⁸ Andrea Vicini, "Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Bioethical Challenges and Approaches," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 620.

⁹ Gregory Arokiaswamy, "Artificial Intelligence within the Context of Economy, Employment and Social Justice," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 633.

¹⁰ Elio Gasda, 651.

¹¹ Elio Gasda, 650.

routine tasks, but could develop more advanced activities with lower costs. In 45 years, intelligent robots will be more skilful than the humans in many tasks, in both efficiency and quality.¹²

In addition to remarkable developments communication, including magnificent assistance with human language and translation skills, the use of artificial intelligence in analysing and interpreting large groups of numbers has also assisted scientific research-and continues still to help both scientific work and business and even political researchers make great strides. One application is the use of “activity data” from communication devices to predict trends for business. Another is the sorting of potential structures for drugs from among millions of possible modifications of a steroid structure, and even finding options that humans may have overlooked.¹³

3. AI and Social Justice

It is time to ask whether social justice would make any sense to AI’s underpinned economy. As we have seen, with AI in all four sectors of the economy (Primary: extraction of raw materials, Secondary: manufacturing finished goods, Tertiary: service, and Quaternary knowledge), the growth would be potentially exponential. Justice calls human beings to deal with others fairly. Fairness is willingly giving to others what they deserve by virtue of their age/gender, relationship, agreement/contract/covenant, work/merit etc. At the prima facie level, justice promotes impartiality, universality, equality, which are all adequately realized through commutative distributive and legal justice. But social analysis reveals that in every society due to various complex reasons, some are pushed to the periphery deviously as rejected and abandoned by the mainstream forces of the society. They often live a miserable, sub-standard, malnourished, undignified, and pathetic life. The

¹² Elio Gasda, 651.

¹³ Patrick Dolan, “Artificial Intelligence: How Close will it come to Being “Made in the Image and Likeness of God?” *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 690.

governments or general public pay no adequate heed to their cry for justice.¹⁴

3.2. AI and Unemployment

Its gradual applications in the economy, are making it capital intensive and consequently has the potential of increasing the economic growth exponentially. Simultaneously it would either displace or disrupt the labour-market. Therefore, the workforce everywhere on the globe, and especially in countries where people are illiterate or backward in AI would become miserably vulnerable as they might become unemployed.¹⁵ Then for the sake of amassing huge profit, it would ruthlessly deny job security for the labourers and send them home without a prick of conscience.¹⁶

3.3. AI and Exploitation of Natural Resources

AI has increased labour productivity and thus so much of finished products are available in the market for sale. For this to occur certainly we have extracted so much of the natural resources. Today we are acutely conscious that resources of the world, especially the non-renewable resources, are limited. Too much exploitation of the natural resources might give exponential economic growth now.¹⁷ Huge productions of goods due to AI, and supplying to market more than demanded, burning the unsold items to retain the brand name, and finally dumping the seas and oceans with waste tell candidly that we are less concerned about the future global citizens.¹⁸

3.4. Mechanization, Dehumanization through AI

AI goes beyond the collection and accumulation of data. “They include the use of information to manipulate behavior, online and offline, in a way that undermines autonomous rational choice. Given users’ intense interaction with data systems and the deep knowledge about individuals this provides, they are vulnerable to “nudges”, manipulation, and deception. “For instance, this is very much

¹⁴ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 636.

¹⁵ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 628.

¹⁶ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 638.

¹⁷ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 637.

¹⁸ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 638.

expressed in gambling, online selling, etc. The advertising agents maximise profit, including exploitation of behavioural biases, deception, and addiction generation. Manipulation of online behavior is becoming a core business model of the Internet.

The manipulation of the behavioral patterns is expressed during the time of the election as well. Social media is now the prime location for political propaganda and manipulation. This influence can be used to steer voting behavior. Definitely, it affects the autonomy of individual. Civil liberties and the protection of individual rights are under intense pressure and privacy protection has diminished massively by negative employment of AI.

It is opined that humans will be prone to be interested in sex and companionship with robots. Humans have long deep emotional attachments to objects, so perhaps companionship with robots. As the result, the manufacturing of the sexual tools is up in rise. In this regard there are concerns in matters of sex. Generally speaking, human behaviour is influenced by¹⁹ experience, and it is likely that pornography or sex robots support the perception of other humans as mere objects of desire, or even recipients of abuse, and thus ruin a deeper sexual and erotic experience. Is it an aberration as far as human life in all its ethics is concerned?

Another important area is the production of wealth. By using artificial intelligence, a company can drastically cut down on relying on the human workforce, and this means that revenues will go to fewer people. It seems clear that AI and robotics will lead to significant gains in productivity and thus overall wealth. The world economy is controlled by wealthy nations and they control it with higher productivity and philosophy of the modern phenomenon of growth. Naturally, when productivity is accelerated by means of machines, the manpower becomes fewer.²⁰

¹⁹ Rajesh Kavalackal, "Artificial Intelligence: An Anthropological and Theological Investigation," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 707.

²⁰ Rajesh Kavalackal, 708.

4. The Impact of AI on Indian Context

In the Indian context, the sense of social justice has to be understood mainly from the backdrop of casteism, religious fundamentalism and male domination.²¹ In our age of globalization and digitalization (AI), the poor people are made to feel poignantly that they are “unwanted” in this new economic and cultural system. Since AI and robotics are increasingly employed in low-skilled jobs, the socio-economically poor who are employed in this sector are thrown out abrasively.²²

The Indian society where age-old social discrimination and economic disparity are still not dismantled; the State had introduced “Reservation Policy.” This policy allots a certain percentage of seats in the education, employment and political fields to the backward and oppressed castes (Scheduled castes). With the recent entry of AI technology into economy, which is already elite-centric through LGP (Liberalization, Globalization, Privatization), the government is keen and quick in handing over the public sectors to the private entrepreneurs.²³ Like this would weaken the reservation policy. The private entrepreneurs very rarely would have a social vision of the wellbeing of the poor, instead they would devise economic strategy of multiplying their profits. With the loss of economic security due to impoverished reservation policy, many of the SCs and STs are going to be either jobless or become part of informal economy (unorganized sector).²⁴

4.1. The Poor: As Victims of Technology

While describing ‘Digital India,’ the Government of India says that it has three key vision areas. They are 1. Digital Infrastructure as a Core Utility to Every Citizen, 2. Governance & Services on Demand, 3. Digital Empowerment of Citizens. Indeed, lofty goals to be achieved! The policy sounds terrific. What about the ground realities? As early as November 2016, after a year of the digital India launch, Javed Anver of India Today points out to poor connectivity,

²¹ Elio Gasda, 640.

²² Elio Gasda, 641.

²³ Elio Gasda, 641.

²⁴ Elio Gasda, 642.

too much load on the network, slowing down or failing payment gateways and India not having a robust telecom network as some of the reasons for the digital projects' failure. Not only the failure in technical infrastructure but also millions of people are still poor in their capacity to buy, understand and manage the latest digital advancements.²⁵

5. The Church's Standpoint on AI

Today the Church sees scientific advancements not as a threat but as a creative blessing! Gone are the days of Copernican confrontations! The Church welcomes development, but scrutinizes them with a rigorous moral and ethical lens!²⁶ Therefore, the enhancement of technical intelligence beneficial to humanity is excellent and is welcome and needs to be progressed. On the other hand, idiocy that is manifested as evil, wicked, criminal and coarse needs to be curbed. This is for the simple reason, that the human person is the recipient of the wonderful blessing called 'intelligence.'²⁷

God had bestowed on the human person abundant natural intelligence. This intelligence, together with the reasoning capacity enables us to know and adore God. Christianity believes that God endows the human person with a superb brain. The human person is expected to develop it to achieve.²⁸

The Church upholds the conviction of the intrinsic priority of the person over things, and of human labour over capital. For the Church: in the process of production, "labour is always a primary efficient cause, while capital, the whole collection of means of production, remains a mere instrument or instrumental cause."²⁹

²⁵ Sahayaraj Stanley, "Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Intelligence, and the Technocratic Paradigm: An Indian Perspective," *Asian Horizons* 14, no.3, (September 2020), 666.

²⁶ Sahayaraj Stanley, 662.

²⁷ Sahayaraj Stanley, 663.

²⁸ Sahayaraj Stanley, 661.

²⁹ Pope John Paul II, *Laborem exercens*, 12.

6. Implications for Meaningful Life

AI will create new perspectives on human reality, human dignity, and the meaning of life. The positive effects in all scientific and machine advancement and it helps us to rationalize many human ambiguities and sorrows and therefore explain them in a positive way so much so that most of the problems of humankind could be solved.³⁰

AI leaves room for our intuitive self-understanding because the image of God tells us a story about our creation and our biological system. The biblical stories of creation reveal that living beings as creatures created by God. On that ground, God's creative powers are mirrored in AI. All human scientific and technological advancements also tell us a story about the human creative powers that are a part of the image of God. AI can be seen as a result of our God-given imagination and courage to be co-creators by creating something new.³¹

The present crisis in the machine age, especially in AI age, is not the unlimited amount of the products in the global market but a new integration between technological means with human life. It demands a hierarchy of ends for humans based on their dynamic nature, spiritual and moral principles, and all the more on the integration and meaning for human life.

The dehumanization of human being therefore is not due to the machine but to idolatry. This idolatry can be explained in terms of false meaning and value given to the procurement of the temporal goods in the sole anthropomorphic world view.³²

The primacy of things in the modern age is not the triumph of techniques and production. It must be interpreted in terms of the relationship between human freedom and natural society. According to Niebuhr the root cause of the disorder is not the abundance of things, but the false meaning given to things by humans which is idolatry. As far as meaning for life is concerned the material goods

³⁰ Rajesh Kavalackal, 711.

³¹ Rajesh Kavalackal, 712.

³² Rajesh Kavalackal, 703.

should be better used for the enhancement and wellbeing of humanity as whole.³³

An International Document in 2019, the High-Level Expert Group on AI of the European Commission published the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence.

1. Respect for human autonomy
2. Prevention of harm (e.g., protection of human dignity as well as mental and physical integrity, with greater attention to vulnerable persons)
3. Fairness (including equality, as well as avoiding bias and discrimination)
4. Explicability (with reference to ‘black box’ algorithms³⁴)³⁵

Conclusion

AI is becoming part and parcel of our life. We wonder at the smartness and efficiency of AI because it has the potential: to give exponential economic growth, prolong our lifespan, increase the quantum/quality of our connectivity, possess better prediction of future. The UN emphasizes that people and their capabilities should be the ultimate criteria for assessing the development of a country, not economic growth alone. The HDI (Human Development Issue) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable, and having a decent standard of living. To improve HDI, today we have to use AI with the principles of social justice.

As disciples of Jesus, we need to build solidarity with the poor as well as have the wisdom to see the intimate connection between the “cry of the earth and cry of the poor.” AI can

³³ Rajesh Kavalackal, 704.

³⁴ A **black box algorithm** is one where the user cannot see the inner workings of the algorithm. It is a rather controversial system, due to the secrecy they contain and the lack of transparency, although its creators defend it as a security and privacy system to avoid data leaks and unfair competition. (<https://www.arimetrics.com/en/digital-glossary/black-box-algorithm>, accessed on 30.01.2023.

³⁵ Andrea Vicini, 623 – 624.

replace a human being as a ‘tool’, never as a ‘person’; AI can be a help, not a helper. So, we need to stand by the poor (caused by AI), because it is in the company and the call of marginalized people that the prophetic voice of the Church becomes vital, radical, and relevant.” Admittedly the Church wants every government to regulate the development and deployment of AI according to the algor-ethics so that the dignity of every human person, especially the poor is well secured.³⁶

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³⁶ Gregory Arokiaswamy, 643.

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